

**CPD ARTICLE: Digital Twins in Construction and Retrofit
(By Hamedreza Esmaeili)**

Date of CPD Completion: 10 December 2025

CPD Type: Self-Directed Learning

Duration: 2 hours

Platform: CIOB MyCPD / CIBSE mycareerpath

Topic: Digital Twins

Digital Twins in Construction and Retrofit – A Personal CPD Reflection

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Topic: Digital Twins – Practical Use in Construction and Retrofit

I had heard about Digital Twins before, but honestly, I didn't fully understand what they really were or how they could help in our real construction or retrofit work until this year. I first got interested when I read an article by CIBSE about using digital twins for live monitoring of retrofitted

buildings.

My Simple Understanding of Digital Twin

Now after studying more, my understanding is that a digital twin is a live digital model of a real building that receives and analyses real-time data from the physical world. For example, after retrofitting a school or house, we can use BIM and sensors to create a digital version of that building, showing things like internal temperature, humidity, energy use, or air quality.

How is it different from BIM?

Many people confuse it with BIM, and I did too. But the key difference is that BIM is mainly for design and construction, while the digital twin comes into action after the building is completed. It becomes a live system that collects and monitors real-time performance data.

My Site Experience with Retrofit Projects

In one of the retrofit projects I was involved in, in Edgbaston, we applied EWI and upgraded the ventilation. But still, we were not sure if the performance was improved. If we had a digital twin, we could have seen clearly which areas were underperforming—maybe the ground floor room still had high humidity or one wall was not retaining heat properly.

Tools I Researched

During my CPD, I learned that companies like Autodesk (BIM 360) and Siemens (NX and MindSphere) are leading in digital twin technology. Some retrofit projects use IoT sensors like AICO or Switchee to collect live data for this purpose.

Why Digital Twins Matter in Retrofit

For retrofit professionals like us, digital twins are highly useful. They help validate whether the retrofit measures like IWI, heat pumps, or PV panels are truly delivering results in terms of comfort and efficiency. Especially for monitoring damp, air quality, or heat loss, they are critical because they allow early detection of failure.

Challenges and Practical Issues

Of course, digital twin systems are still expensive to implement for small domestic projects. But for care homes, housing blocks or public buildings with larger budgets, I believe it is a strong investment for the future.

My Personal Conclusion

This CPD session helped me prepare for the future. I believe digital twins are not just a futuristic idea—they are already being adopted in practice. For someone like me aiming to become a Chartered Surveyor or Retrofit Manager, learning about this gives me a competitive edge. I've now logged this learning into my 2025 CPD record and hope to start testing digital monitoring with RH sensors in upcoming projects.

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